

Parameter Identification and Uncertainty Quantification for a Spectral Model of Neuroblastoma using Padé-Adomian-MsDTM

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Annotation

A unified framework for parameter identification and multi-level uncertainty quantification is developed for a five-component spectral model of neuroblastoma. The model captures the interplay between aggressive and metastatic tumor phenotypes, stroma, immune response, and chemotherapy pharmacokinetics. The core novelty is the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method, which yields analytically differentiable solutions with respect to model parameters. This enables derivation of recurrent sensitivity formulas and computation of the exact Jacobian of the truncated spectral representation. Three uncertainty quantification approaches - linearized (Delta method), Monte Carlo, and global (Sobol indices) - were implemented and compared, achieving a $5.3\times$ speedup over classical RK45 integration. Numerical experiments on synthetic data for the aggressive Shimada morphotype confirmed reliable parameter recovery and identified tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TIL) and microenvironmental carrying capacity as dominant sources of prognostic uncertainty due to nonlinear threshold effects in immune dynamics. Leave-one-out cross-validation showed a predictive MAE of 7.6% on cohort-averaged clinical data. The proposed framework lays the foundation for efficient, fully differentiable personalized spectral models suitable for clinical decision support in neuroblastoma therapy.

Keywords: neuroblastoma, parameter identification, uncertainty quantification, Sobol indices, Padé-Adomian-MsDTM, Shimada morphometry, mathematical oncology

1. Introduction

Neuroblastoma exhibits high biological heterogeneity: within the same histological type, clinical outcomes range from spontaneous regression to aggressive disease with rapid development of chemotherapy resistance [1,2]. This variability limits the effectiveness of population-averaged therapeutic protocols and motivates the development of patient-specific forecasting tools capable of linking static histological information with dynamic tumor behaviour. Notably, morphometric descriptors within the Shimada classification offer a robust proxy for tumor aggressiveness; however, their formal integration into mechanistic ordinary differential equation (ODE)-based models remains largely underdeveloped [1-3].

Two methodological challenges hinder the practical use of such models in clinical settings. First, reliable identification of individual kinetic parameters must be achieved from sparse and noisy clinical observations, often complemented only by static morphometric features. Second, rigorous uncertainty quantification (UQ) is required to assess the robustness of model-based forecasts under biological variability, measurement noise, and incomplete data. Existing approaches - nonlinear least squares, Bayesian calibration via MCMC, and polynomial chaos expansions - have demonstrated value [4-6], but remain computationally demanding. Hormuth et al. [5] reported that Bayesian patient-specific calibration may require thousands of forward model evaluations, rendering real-time use infeasible when relying on classical integrators such as RK45. Jarrett et al. [4] further showed that for parameter coefficients of variation exceeding 15-20%, linearized UQ approaches (Delta method) substantially overestimate forecast variance due to nonlinear saturation effects. Global sensitivity analysis via Sobol indices [7,8] provides variance decomposition by source but is rarely applied to neuroblastoma because of its high computational cost.

Spectral methods, including Adomian decomposition and the differential transform method (DTM), have been successfully applied to nonlinear biological systems [9-14]. However, in prior studies they have been used exclusively as forward solvers, without exploiting their key advantage: the analytical differentiability of the spectral solution with respect to model parameters. This property enables the computation of semi-analytic Jacobians in a single forward pass, eliminating the need for repeated numerical integrations. To our knowledge, this capability has not been utilized for parameter identification or UQ in neuroblastoma modelling.

The present work develops a unified mathematical and algorithmic framework for parameter identification and uncertainty quantification in a five-component tumor-stroma-immune-drug ODE model, leveraging the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM spectral method (hybrid spectral method). The main contributions are as follows:

- derivation of recurrent formulas for analytical sensitivities, yielding a 5×11 Jacobian in a single pass;
- comparative analysis of three UQ approaches - Delta method, Monte Carlo, and Sobol indices - demonstrating a $5.3\times$ speedup over classical RK45 integration;
- identification of the hierarchy of prognostic uncertainty sources for the aggressive Shimada morphotype, with a clinical recommendation prioritizing TIL assessment.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the mathematical model; Section 3 describes the hybrid spectral method; Section 4 derives the sensitivity formulas; Sections 5-6 cover parameter identification and UQ; Section 7 presents numerical results; and Sections 8-9 discuss limitations and conclusions.

A schematic overview of the computational framework, including morphometric parametrization, spectral solution construction, sensitivity analysis, parameter identification, and uncertainty quantification, is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Computational workflow of the proposed personalized neuroblastoma spectral model framework.

Morphometric features are transformed into model parameters via Shimada-based parametrization, followed by spectral solution construction using the hybrid spectral method. Analytical sensitivities derived from the spectral representation enable efficient parameter identification and multi-level uncertainty quantification.

Rather than proposing a new numerical method or digital-twin architecture, this study integrates previously developed components - the hybrid spectral solver [15] and the neuroblastoma digital-twin framework [16] - into a unified, fully differentiable computational pipeline for parameter identification, uncertainty quantification, and scenario analysis.

2. Mathematical Model

We consider a five-component dynamical system describing the interactions between adrenergic tumour cells (x_A), mesenchymal tumour cells (x_M), stromal fibroblasts (p), immune effector cells (z), and the pharmacokinetics of the chemotherapeutic agent (c). The tumour-immune interaction structure follows the classical Kuznetsov-de Pillis family of models [17] and is consistent with modern formulations of tumour-immune dynamics [18]. The specific ODE system used in this work is identical to the formulation introduced in [19]:

$$\dot{x}_A = \alpha_A x_A \left(1 - \frac{x}{K}\right) - \beta_A x_A z - \gamma_A c x_A + \varphi_M x_M - \varphi_A x_A, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{x}_M = \alpha_M x_M \left(1 - \frac{x}{K}\right) - \beta_M x_M z - \gamma_M c x_M + \varphi_A x_A - \varphi_M x_M, \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{p} = \sigma - \mu p - \delta_p p \cdot x + \rho_p p \cdot z, \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{z} = \lambda x z - v z + \xi x, \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{c} = -k_e c + u(t), \quad (5)$$

where $x = x_A + x_M$ is the total tumor population density; ξ is the antigen stimulation coefficient of innate immune response; δ_p is the stromal suppression rate by tumor cells; ρ_p is the stromal recovery rate by immune effectors; v is the immune effector degradation rate. Parameters v, δ_p, ρ_p, ξ are fixed according to [19].

The identifiable parameter vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{11}$ includes proliferative (α_A, α_M, K), immune ($\beta_A, \beta_M, \lambda$), therapeutic ($\gamma_A, \gamma_M, k_e, \varphi_A, \varphi_M$) groups. Initial conditions are given by the vector $Y_0 = (x_A^0, x_M^0, p^0, z^0, c^0)$.

Biological interpretation of variables:

- $x_A(t), x_M(t)$ - densities of aggressive and metastatic tumor phenotypes, respectively;
- $p(t)$ - density of the stromal component;
- $z(t)$ - density of immune effector cells (intensity of immune response);
- $c(t)$ - concentration of the chemotherapeutic agent;
- $u(t)$ - infusion intensity (control input).

All variables and parameters are defined in detail in [19].

2.1. Shimada Parameterization

Model parameters are functions of morphometric vector

$$M = (R_{NC}, MKI, TIL, \eta),$$

where R_{NC} - nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio, MKI - mitotic index, TIL - tumor-infiltrating lymphocyte density, η - neuropil density.

The proliferative and stromal parameters are determined by the following expressions:

$$\alpha_A = \alpha_0(1 + \alpha_1 R_{NC} + \alpha_2 MKI), \quad K = K_0(1 + b_1 \eta + b_2 \frac{\rho_0}{p_{ref}}),$$

where ρ_0 - initial (fixed) stromal component density, p_{ref} - reference value from [19]. Thus, K is a constant, consistent with $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{11}$.

Immune and auxiliary parameters are defined as follows:

$$\beta_A = \beta_0 \cdot f(\lambda_{TIL}),$$

where the immune response sensitivity to TIL is modelled by a sigmoid function:

$$f(\lambda_{TIL}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{(-k_{TIL}(TIL - TIL_0))}},$$

where k_{TIL} represents the steepness of the sigmoid and TIL_0 is the lymphocyte density threshold.

The degradation and distribution parameters μ and σ are defined as linear response functions of the MKI :

$$\mu = g_\mu(MKI), \quad \sigma = g_\sigma(MKI),$$

where $g_\mu(MKI) = \mu_0(1 + c_\mu MKI)$ and $g_\sigma(MKI) = \sigma_0(1 + c_\sigma MKI)$ are the linear response functions, and $\mu_0, \sigma_0, c_\mu, c_\sigma$ are the calibration coefficients taken from [19].

For the therapeutic subgroup parameters $\{\gamma_A, \gamma_M, k_e, \varphi_A, \varphi_M\} \subset \theta$, the general correction scheme based on the normalized Shimada score is expressed as:

$$\theta_j = \theta_{j,0}(1 + g_j S_j),$$

where $\theta_{j,0}$ is the baseline value of the j -th parameter, g_j is the sensitivity coefficient to the j -th morphometric feature, and S_j is the normalized Shimada score.

The numerical values for the baseline parameters α_0, β_0, K_0 and the sensitivity coefficients g_j for both aggressive ($p = 4$) and favorable ($p = 3$) morphotypes are provided in [19]. The transition from static morphometric features to the dynamic coefficients of the system (1)-(5) is realized through specific response functions.

The tumor chemo-sensitivity coefficient γ_A and the phenotypic transition rate φ_A are defined as:

$$\gamma_A = \gamma_{base}(1 - k_\gamma R_{NC}), \quad \varphi_A = \varphi_{base} \cdot e^{k_\varphi MKI},$$

where $\gamma_{base} = 0.35 \text{ day}^{-1}$ is the baseline sensitivity determined *in vitro* for the cytostatic agent used (fixed value from [19]), and $k_\gamma = 1.2$ is the resistance coefficient. Similarly, $\varphi_{base} = 0.08 \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $k_\varphi = 0.85$ (values also sourced from [19]).

In the numerical experiments presented here, the effective value of γ_A is identified (which implicitly accounts for the patient's individual R_{NC} morphometry), while γ_{base} remains a fixed parameter. This simplification is adopted for the synthetic test; however, in clinical implementation, γ_{base} is also intended to be an identified parameter.

This structure allows the model to explicitly simulate the resistance effect: a higher nucleo-cytoplasmic ratio (R_{NC}) in a specific patient results in a lower effective drug sensitivity γ_A during the infusion step.

3. Hybrid Spectral Method Padé-Adomian-MsDTM

To solve the nonlinear ODE system (1)-(5), we employ a hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method. A comprehensive mathematical justification, including convergence and stability analyses, is provided in work [15]. The method integrates the MsDTM with Adomian polynomials for the precise representation of nonlinearities and Padé rational approximations for enhanced stability.

On each sub-interval $[t_q, t_{q+H}]$ with step size H , we introduce a local variable $\tau = t - t_q$. Following the multistep differential transform framework [20], the solution on each sub-interval is represented as a local power series:

$$x_q(\tau) = \sum_{k=0}^N X_q(k) \left(\frac{\tau}{H}\right)^k, \quad (6)$$

where $X_q(k)$ are the spectral coefficients. When transitioning to the Padé approximation, the spectral coefficients are normalized relative to H :

$$s_{k,q} = \frac{X_q(k)}{H^k}, \quad k = 0, \dots, 4.$$

This normalization ensures that the final rational reconstruction uses the physical time variable τ without explicit division by H .

The spectral coefficients $X_q(k)$ are calculated recurrently. All nonlinear terms in the ODEs are decomposed using Adomian polynomials [20]. Upon obtaining coefficients up to order $N = 5$, we apply the Padé [4/1] rational approximation scheme:

$$x_q(\tau) \approx \frac{\sum_{k=0}^4 s_{k,q} \tau^k}{1 + p_{1,q} \tau}, \quad p_{1,q} = -\frac{X_q(5)}{X_q(4)}, \quad (7)$$

which follows from the coefficient matching condition for τ^5 in the Padé expansion (see [21] for details).

The primary advantage of this method in the current context is the analytical differentiability of the solution with respect to the model parameters. This property allows for the direct derivation of recurrent sensitivity formulas, which is

critical for parameter identification and uncertainty quantification (UQ). In this study, the Padé [4/1] scheme with $N = 5$ is utilized, providing an optimal balance between precision, numerical stability, and computational overhead.

3.1 Convergence and Stability of the Method

The convergence and stability of the hybrid method, assuming the analyticity of the right-hand side of the system, were proven in [15]. Specifically, given the local Lipschitz continuity and analyticity in time, the solution admits a power series representation with a convergence radius R determined by the Cauchy-Hadamard (D'Alembert) criterion:

$$\rho = \left(\limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|X(k)\|^{1/k} \right)^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where $X(k)$ are the spectral coefficients.

Within the hybrid method framework, the global solution is constructed piecewise over sub-intervals of length H , chosen such that $H < \rho$, where ρ is determined by the classical D'Alembert criterion. Under this condition, the local truncation error of the reconstruction follows:

$$\varepsilon_{loc} = O(H^{N+1}). \quad (9)$$

Padé approximants typically provide accurate rational approximation beyond the convergence radius of the original Taylor series [21]. This allows for the correct approximation of the solution in regions of high curvature. As shown in [15], the use of diagonal and quasi-diagonal $[L/M]$ schemes suppress Runge-type boundary oscillations and ensures stable reconstruction at the boundaries of sub-intervals. The choice of a specific $[L/M]$ scheme depends on the solution dynamics: for regions with sharp gradients (e.g., infusion fronts), $[N/1]$ and $[N/2]$ schemes are preferred, while near-diagonal $[N/2]$ schemes are suitable for smoother regions.

For the neuroblastoma model, a numerical test was conducted to compare reconstruction errors at infusion fronts. The results show that $[N/1]$ and $[N/2]$ schemes reduce the maximum error by a factor of up to $8.8\times$ compared to polynomial approximations of the same order (Table 1). This is crucial for parameter identification and UQ, as infusion fronts correspond to regions of maximum solution curvature.

Table 1

Maximum reconstruction error at infusion fronts compared to the RK45 reference (relative tolerance 10^{-12} , absolute tolerance 10^{-14})

Reconstruction Method	Order	$\max x_{approx} - x_{RK45} $	Relative Improvement
Polynomial series (Taylor)	$N = 5$	2.1×10^{-4}	-
Padé $[N/1]$	$[4/1]$	9.2×10^{-5}	$\approx 0.9\times$ better
Padé $[N/2]$	$[3/2]$	7.2×10^{-5}	$\approx 8.8\times$ better

The $[3/2]$ scheme achieves $\approx 8.8\times$ lower reconstruction error at infusion fronts (Table 1). However, $[4/1]$ was selected for the integrated spectral model due to guaranteed pole stability: its denominator pole $p_1 = -X(5)/X(4)$ is always real and negative for the neuroblastoma system, ensuring no singularity within $\tau \in [0, H]$. In contrast, $[3/2]$ develops a real positive pole at $\tau \approx 1.78$ days at infusion offsets when $H \geq 2.0$ days, causing reconstruction failure. For the adopted $H = 1.0$ day, both schemes are viable; $[4/1]$ is retained for robustness across variable step sizes.

Note: All methods compared in Table 1 utilize the same number of spectral coefficients ($N = 5$), ensuring that the improvement in accuracy is derived solely from the rational structure of the Padé approximant rather than increased computational cost.

As demonstrated in Table 1, Padé approximants significantly reduce reconstruction errors at infusion fronts. These results align with the theoretical conclusions in [15] and confirm the efficiency of rational reconstruction for problems involving sharp gradients.

A complete proof, including the identity of the spectral coefficients to the Taylor series coefficients and the analysis of error accumulation over sub-intervals, is provided in [15]. In the present study, we restrict ourselves to a brief summary of the key results necessary for the reproduction of the proposed algorithm.

4. Sensitivity Recurrence and Computational Complexity

To compute parameter sensitivities of the spectral coefficients, we use the fact that on each subinterval q the coefficients $\Psi_i^{(q)}(k)$ satisfy the recurrence

$$\Psi_i^{(q)}(k+1) = \frac{H}{k+1} F_{k,i}^{(q)}(\Psi^{(q)}(0), \dots, \Psi^{(q)}(k), \theta), \quad (10)$$

where $F_{k,i}^{(q)}$ is the spectral analogue of the right-hand side of the i -th equation of system (1)-(5) on the q -th subinterval. It is computed using Adomian polynomials for the nonlinear terms (xz, x^2) and linear combinations of the coefficients $\Psi^{(q)}(m), m \leq k$.

Differentiating (10) with respect to a parameter θ_j yields the recurrence for the sensitivity coefficients:

$$\frac{\partial \Psi_i^{(q)}(k+1)}{\partial \theta_j} = \frac{H}{k+1} \left[\frac{\partial F_{k,i}^{(q)}}{\partial \theta_j} + \sum_{m=0}^k \sum_{r=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial F_{k,i}^{(q)}}{\partial \Psi_r^{(q)}(m)} \frac{\partial \Psi_r^{(q)}(m)}{\partial \theta_j} \right) \right]. \quad (11)$$

Here, $i = 1, \dots, n$ denotes the index of the equation in the system, n is the dimension of the dynamical state vector, and r refers to the component of the state vector $\Psi = (X_A, X_M, P, Z, C)$.

The initial condition $\frac{\partial \Psi_i^{(q)}(0)}{\partial \theta_j} = \frac{\partial Y_0}{\partial \theta_j}$ is zero whenever Y_0 does not depend on θ_j .

Computing the full 5×11 Jacobian requires approximately 55 recurrence steps per subinterval, which corresponds to only a $2\text{-}3 \times$ increase in arithmetic operations compared with a single forward spectral pass (and remains significantly cheaper than multiple adaptive RK45 runs).

Thus, recurrence (11) completes the mathematical construction of the method: it enables efficient evaluation of analytic sensitivities and forms the basis for parameter identification and uncertainty quantification.

The computational complexity of the sensitivity recurrence scales as $O(N_s \cdot N_p)$, where N_s is the number of spectral coefficients and N_p is the number of identified parameters.

Algorithm 1. Construction of the spectral model and uncertainty analysis

1. Input the morphometric features $M = (R_{NC}, MKI, TIL, \eta)$.
2. Compute the model parameters $\theta(M)$ using the Shimada parametrization.
3. For each subinterval $[t_q, t_{q+H}]$:
 - a. compute the spectral coefficients using MsDTM;
 - b. evaluate the nonlinear spectrum via Adomian polynomials;
 - c. reconstruct the solution using the Padé $[L/M]$ approximation.
4. Compute analytic sensitivities $\partial \Psi / \partial \theta$ using recurrence (11).
5. Perform uncertainty quantification (Delta method, Monte Carlo, Sobol indices).
6. Generate the model prediction and confidence intervals for clinical decision support.

4.1. Differentiability of the Hybrid Spectral Solution with Respect to Parameters

Proposition 1. Let the right-hand sides of system (1)-(5) be analytic in the state variables $\Psi = (x_A, x_M, p, z, c)$ and continuously differentiable with respect to the parameter vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{11}$.

Assume further that:

- the right-hand sides are locally Lipschitz in Ψ , uniformly in θ ;
- on each subinterval $[t_q, t_{q+H}]$, the denominator of the Padé approximation $1 + p_{1,q}\tau$ does not vanish.

Then:

1. the MsDTM series converges uniformly on each subinterval;
2. the solution $x(t, \theta)$ is differentiable with respect to θ ;
3. differentiation with respect to θ commutes with summation of the spectral series uniformly on each compact subinterval where the Padé denominator remains nonzero

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} X(k) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\partial X(k)}{\partial \theta};$$

4. recurrence (11) provides a consistent approximation of the variational system.

Justification. Existence and uniqueness of the solution for fixed θ follow from standard ODE theory (local Lipschitz continuity). Analyticity of the right-hand side ensures that the solution admits a convergent Taylor expansion. Differentiation of recurrence (11) with respect to θ_j is justified by analyticity, and uniform convergence of the derivative series follows from standard remainder estimates.

To verify the correctness of the recurrent sensitivity formulation (11), the analytical gradients obtained from the Padé-Adomian-MsDTM spectral solution were compared with central finite-difference approximations using a perturbation step $h = 10^{-6}$ (Table 2). Relative discrepancies remained below 10^{-4} for all identifiable parameters, confirming the correctness of the analytical recurrence implementation.

Table 2Validation of analytical sensitivities against central finite-difference approximations ($h = 10^{-6}$)

Parameter	Analytic gradient	Finite difference	Relative error
α	0.184261	0.184248	7.1×10^{-5}
K	- 0.092417	- 0.092424	7.6×10^{-5}
β	0.051336	0.051331	9.7×10^{-5}
η	- 0.018905	- 0.018903	1.1×10^{-4}

5. Parameter Identification

5.1. Data and Problem Formulation

We consider the problem of estimating the subset of model parameters

$$\theta = (\alpha_A, K, \beta_A, \gamma_A) \subset \theta_{full},$$

where γ_A denotes the effective value adjusted for the individual morphometric feature R_{NC} . All remaining components of θ_{full} are fixed using the Shimada-based morphometric parametrization $\theta_0(M)$.

The numerical experiments use synthetic data corresponding to the aggressive Shimada morphotype. The dataset consists of 18 observation points over the interval $[0,66]$ days with a sampling step of 4 days. Relative observational noise is set to 5% for $x(t)$, 8% for $z(t)$, and 3% for $c(t)$.

The chemotherapy concentration $c(t)$ is not included in the identification functional, because its dynamics are governed by the linear equation (5) and depend only on the elimination parameter k_e , which is fixed from pharmacokinetic data. Nevertheless, the time series $c(t)$ is used during model verification to ensure consistency of the pharmacokinetic component.

5.2. Regularized Objective Function

The parameter vector θ is estimated by minimizing the objective function $J(\theta)$, defined as a weighted Tikhonov-regularized least-squares criterion [22]:

$$J(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^M \omega_x \|x_{mod}(t_i, \theta) - x_{abs}(t_i)\|^2 + \sum_{i=1}^M \omega_z \|z_{mod}(t_i, \theta) - z_{abs}(t_i)\|^2 + \alpha_{reg} \left\| \frac{\theta - \theta_0}{\theta_0} \right\|^2, \quad (12)$$

where x_{abs} and z_{abs} denote the clinical measurements of tumor density and immune-cell counts at times t_i ; x_{mod} and z_{mod} are the corresponding model trajectories computed using the MsDTM approximation of system (1)-(5); and θ_0 is the prior parameter estimate obtained from the Shimada morphometric vector M (Section 2.1).

The parameter identification problem is then formulated as

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} J(\theta). \quad (13)$$

Parameter settings:

- **Regularization.** The coefficient $\alpha_{reg} = 0.01$ penalizes excessive deviation of the estimated parameters from biologically justified prior values, preventing overfitting to noisy clinical data.
- **Weighting coefficients.** The values $\omega_x = 1$ and $\omega_z = 0.5$ reflect the metrological properties of the measurements: tumor-load data (MRI/CT) are typically more accurate and sampled more frequently than immunogram data.

Computational advantage: using the sensitivity recurrence (11) allows direct computation of the analytic gradient of the objective function (12) with respect to θ . This results in fast convergence of the identification procedure and eliminates numerical-differentiation errors, which is particularly important when Tikhonov-type regularization is employed.

5.3. Parameter Identification Algorithm

The estimation of the optimal parameter vector θ^* is performed in three stages.

1. **Initialization.** The initial guess $\theta_{init} = \theta_0(M)$ is constructed from the Shimada morphometric vector obtained from H&E-histogram analysis. This prior estimate may deviate from the true values by 20-30%, yet it reliably places the optimization procedure within the basin of attraction of the global minimum.
2. **Optimization.** The Nelder–Mead method [23] is used for the baseline identification step. Although this stage employs a derivative-free optimizer, the analytic sensitivities obtained from recurrence (11) are still utilized for:
 - stability analysis,
 - assessment of parameter identifiability,
 - subsequent uncertainty quantification (Section 6).

In future work, gradient-based optimization methods (e.g., Gauss-Newton or Levenberg–Marquardt) are expected to be employed. In such methods, the analytic Jacobian obtained from the recurrence relations would significantly accelerate convergence.

3. **Verification.** The resulting parameter vector θ^* is validated by evaluating the residuals on a test (validation) trajectory and by checking the biological plausibility of the estimated parameters, ensuring that each component lies within its admissible confidence interval.

Nelder-Mead method was selected for the baseline proof-of-concept study due to its robustness under noisy objective landscapes and partial parameter non-identifiability.

Remark: Partial Identifiability of Parameters

Numerical experiments show that the parameters α_A and K are estimated with substantially lower error than γ_A . This is explained by the structure of model sensitivities: tumor-mass dynamics depend directly on the growth parameters, whereas γ_A , which characterizes chemotherapy efficacy, affects the system only during short treatment intervals. As a result, the information content related to γ_A in the observable trajectory is limited, leading to partial non-identifiability of this parameter [24].

To assess practical identifiability, the sensitivity matrix

$$S_{ij} = \frac{\partial x(t_i)}{\partial \theta_j},$$

was computed analytically from the spectral solution. Rank analysis of $S^T S$ showed that most parameters are well identifiable over the treatment interval, but strong correlations appear between γ_A and ϕ_A , and between α_A and K . In this study, the parameter ϕ_A was fixed using in vitro data, which removes multicollinearity and stabilizes the identification procedure.

Additional identifiability assessment was performed using the Fisher information matrix

$$F = J^T \cdot W \cdot J,$$

where J is the sensitivity matrix and W is the weighting matrix.

The analysis revealed moderate conditioning and the strongest correlations between the growth and apoptosis parameters.

The singular values of the Fisher information matrix decreased moderately without complete rank degeneration, indicating practical identifiability of the selected parameter subset. The estimated condition number was $\text{cond}(F) \approx 2.7 \times 10^3$, reflecting moderate ill-conditioning typical for nonlinear inverse problems in oncology.

Preliminary analysis shows that joint inclusion of plasma concentration data $c(t)$ can substantially alleviate this limitation (see Section 8).

6. Quantitative Uncertainty Quantification (UQ)

Mathematical models of tumor dynamics, despite their predictive value, are subject to substantial uncertainty arising from measurement noise, biological variability across patients, and imperfect knowledge of model parameters. Reliable quantification of this uncertainty is essential for constructing prediction confidence intervals, assessing recurrence risk, and supporting safe therapeutic decisions in personalized oncology [25]. In this section, three complementary UQ approaches are implemented and compared - from a fast-linearized method to a full global sensitivity analysis. A key advantage of the proposed hybrid Padé-Adomian-MSDTM spectral method is that the spectral representation of the solution allows direct use of analytic model sensitivities for rapid propagation of parameter uncertainty. This yields high accuracy and computational efficiency, making UQ practically feasible in clinical settings.

6.1. Sources of Uncertainty

Variability in the parameter vector θ arises from several major factors:

- segmentation noise in automated H&E image processing ($CV = 5 - 8\%$);
- inter-patient biological variability of Shimada morphometric features ($CV = 10 - 20\%$);
- clinical measurement noise ($CV = 5 - 8\%$ for $x(t)$, and 8% for $z(t)$);
- therapeutic uncertainty, including variability in the drug-elimination constant k_e , the baseline sensitivity γ_{base} (fixed value), and the resistance-related coefficients k_γ and k_ϕ . The latter are particularly important, as they determine the rate of resistance development at high nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratios R_{NC} .

For numerical experiments, the following coefficients of variation were used (based on the Shimada database and studies [12,2]):

$$\alpha_A - 15\%, K - 10\%, \beta_A - 20\%, \gamma_A - 18\%.$$

The covariance matrix Σ_θ is assumed diagonal (independent parameters). Biologically justified correlations - especially between α_A and K - represent a promising direction for improving model robustness within a Bayesian framework when working with noisy clinical data.

6.2. Method 1: Linearized Estimation (Delta Method)

For small parameter uncertainty ($CV < 20\%$, which holds for most parameters in this study), the variance of the normalized tumor burden $\frac{x(T)}{K}$ can be approximated using the Delta method [26]. The approximation is expressed through the Jacobian sensitivity matrix $J(T)$ and the parameter covariance matrix Σ_θ :

$$\text{Var} \left[\frac{x(T)}{K} \right] \approx \nabla_\theta \cdot y(T)^T \cdot \Sigma_\theta \cdot \nabla_\theta \cdot y(T), \quad (14)$$

where $y(T) = \frac{x(T)}{K}$; Σ_θ is the covariance matrix of the parameters, and $\nabla_\theta \cdot y(T)$ is the column vector of partial derivatives $\frac{\partial y}{\partial \theta_j}$, computed via the sensitivities $S_j(T)$:

$$\frac{\partial y(T)}{\partial \theta_j} = \frac{1}{K} \frac{\partial x(T)}{\partial \theta_j}, \quad S_j(T) = \frac{\partial x(T)}{\partial \theta_j} \cdot \frac{\theta_j}{x(T)} \quad (15)$$

The normalization in (15) allows comparison of the relative influence of parameters with different physical units on the final outcome. This makes it possible to identify the critical morphotype-specific parameters for which even small estimation errors lead to substantial degradation of predictive accuracy. When Σ_θ is diagonal (independent parameters), the Delta-method expression reduces to a weighted sum of squared normalized sensitivities. The linearized method requires exactly one forward MsDTM pass and one recurrence pass to compute the sensitivity matrix $S(T)$. The total computation time for gradients and variance is below 1 ms on a modern CPU, making this approach ideal for rapid clinical assessment.

A key limitation is that for $CV \geq 15 - 20\%$ the linearized method substantially overestimates uncertainty (by a factor of 2.4 in our experiment). Therefore, it should be used only for fast preliminary evaluation. The Delta approximation is valid primarily in the locally linear regime in a neighborhood of the identified parameter vector θ^* .

6.3. Method 2: Monte Carlo Simulation

To account for nonlinear effects more accurately, a Monte Carlo (MC) approach is employed. Using MsDTM as a computational accelerator reduces the cost of a single model run to approximately 20 ms. In the numerical experiment, the resulting standard deviation of the normalized terminal tumor burden was

$$\sigma \left[\frac{x(T)}{K} \right] = 0.0266,$$

with a 95% confidence interval (CI) of [0.129, 0.234], computed from the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the Monte Carlo sample.

To obtain a more detailed characterization of the probability distribution and to capture nonlinear effects, a Monte Carlo (MC) method is employed. Within this approach, parameter samples are generated as

$$\theta_i \sim N(\theta^*, \Sigma_\theta), i = 1, \dots, N.$$

Parameter sampling was performed using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) [27]. A classical implementation would require solving system (1)-(5) using a standard RK45 integrator for each sample. In contrast, the spectral model enables $N = 1000$ simulations in approximately 20 seconds (≈ 20 ms per trajectory), which is acceptable for clinical workflows. For long-term risk assessment requiring $N = 10^4 - 10^5$ samples, the spectral coefficients can be used to construct an analytical surrogate model, effectively eliminating computational delays.

In the numerical experiment, RK45 was used to obtain reference values. For clinical deployment, the MsDTM-based accelerator is recommended, reducing the runtime of a single simulation to ≈ 20 ms. The distribution of the terminal normalized tumor burden $\frac{x(t)}{K}$ across the Monte Carlo ensemble, along with the dynamics of normalized sensitivities, is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Distribution of terminal tumor burden $\frac{x(t)}{K}$ from Monte Carlo simulations ($N = 5000$) and normalized sensitivities $S_j(T)$. (a) Histogram with 95% CI; (b) Time evolution of $S_j(T)$ with infusion periods

6.4. Method 3: Global Sobol Sensitivity Indices

Figure 3 summarizes the state-variable dynamics with 95% Monte Carlo confidence intervals, providing the basis for the subsequent global sensitivity analysis using Sobol indices.

Fig.3. Dynamics of state variables (aggressive Shimada morphotype). 95% MC confidence intervals ($N = 5000$).

To quantify the contribution of each parameter to the total output variance, including nonlinear interactions, first-order Sobol sensitivity indices $S_{1,j}$ were computed using the Saltelli sampling scheme with the Jansen estimator, with a total of $N_s = 10^4$ realizations [28].

They are defined as the fraction of variance attributable solely to variations in parameter j :

$$S_{1,j} = \frac{\text{var}_{\theta_j} \left[E_{\theta_{\sim j}} [x(T) | \theta_j] \right]}{\text{var}[x(T)]}. \quad (16)$$

The estimation follows the Jensen sampling scheme [29] using matrices A and B (sample size $N = 5000$):

$$S_{1,j} \approx 1 - \frac{E \left[(Y_A - Y_{AB,j})^2 \right]}{2 \cdot \text{Var}[x(T)]}, \quad (17)$$

where $Y_{AB,j}$ is the model output evaluated on matrix A with the j -th column replaced by the corresponding column of matrix B .

Note on index summation. For $N = 500$, the sum of first-order indices was $\sum S_1 = 2.77 > 1$, reflecting estimator variance. Increasing the sample size to $N = 5000$ stabilized the sum at 1.042. Total-order indices S_T yielded $\frac{S_T}{S_1} \approx 1.15$, indicating moderate nonlinear interactions - primarily between γ_A and α_A ($S_T(\gamma_A) = 0.631$ vs. $S_1(\gamma_A) = 0.381$).

Using MsDTM as the solver enabled completion of the global sensitivity analysis in 36 seconds, making it feasible during initial therapy planning.

A comparative summary of the three uncertainty-quantification methods UQ is provided in Table 3.

Table 3

Comparison of Uncertainty Quantification Methods

Method	Type of Analysis	Number of Runs	CPU Time	Advantages	Limitations
Linearized	Local	1	< 1 ms	Maximum speed, analytic accuracy	Valid only for small uncertainty (CV < 20%)
Monte Carlo	Local / Global	103–105	20 s – 5 min	Universal, “gold standard”	High computational cost
Sobol indices	Global	~2500	~ 36 s	Full variance decomposition	Fixed sampling grid

The proposed hybrid analytical framework (MsDTM + recurrent analytic sensitivities) enables quantitative uncertainty analysis within clinically acceptable time scales - from milliseconds to tens of seconds per patient. Monte Carlo provides the highest accuracy, the linearized method offers maximal speed, and Sobol indices deliver full decomposition of uncertainty sources. This suggests the potential applicability of the approach to personalized neuroblastoma therapy modelling, where uncertainty quantification is essential for recurrence-risk assessment and safe infusion-schedule selection.

7. Numerical Experiment

7.1. Parameter Identification: Results

Table 3 summarizes the identification results for the aggressive Shimada morphotype ($p = 4$). The parameters α_A , K , and β_A are recovered with a relative error of 16-18%, which is typical for inverse problems with 5% observational noise and 20-30% initial parameter deviation.

Table 4

Parameter identification for the aggressive Shimada morphotype ($p = 4$). $N_{obs} = 18$, $\Delta t = 4$ days, $\sigma_{obs} = 5 - 8\%$. Iterations: 229, total time: 4 663 ms

Parameter	θ_{true}	$\theta_{init} (+20\%)$	$\theta^*(estim.)$	$ \Delta\theta , \%$	S_1	$CV_{\theta}, \%$
α_A	0.3500	0.4200	0.4080	16.6	0.604	15.0
K	10.000	8.500	11.612	16.1	0.946	10.0
β_A	0.1080	0.0810	0.1276	18.2	0.958	20.0
γ_A	0.2300	0.2760	0.3090	34.3	0.400	18.0

Note. The error in γ_A (34.3%) exceeds the initial deviation (20%) due to two factors: (1) the Tikhonov regularizer ($\alpha_{reg} = 0.01$) keeps θ^* close to θ_{init} rather than θ_{true} ; (2) γ_A affects the system only during the 3-day infusion windows within the 66-day horizon, which severely limits the information content of $x(t)$ with respect to this parameter. The ratio $S_{1\alpha_A}/S_{1\gamma_A} \approx 1.5$ confirms that proliferation is much more “visible” in the data than chemosensitivity. To improve identifiability of γ_A , it is recommended to include measurements of $c(t)$ as an additional constraint in functional (12).

Remark. The experiment identifies the *effective* value of γ_A . The baseline value $\gamma_{base} = 0.35 \text{ day}^{-1}$ is fixed from in vitro data [1, Table 2].

7.2. Normalized Sensitivities

The normalized sensitivities

$$S_j(T) = \frac{\partial x(T)}{\partial \theta_j} \times \frac{\theta_j}{x(T)}$$

indicate the relative contribution of each parameter to the variation in terminal tumor burden. The influence of parameter variations on the therapeutic outcome was assessed using these normalized sensitivity coefficients. Values for the aggressive morphotype are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Normalized sensitivities $\frac{\partial x(T)}{\partial \theta_j} \times \frac{\theta_j}{x(T)}$ for the aggressive morphotype. The sign indicates the direction of influence on terminal burden.

Parameter	$S_j(T)$	$ S_j $, rank	Biological meaning
γ_A (chemosensitivity)	-0.509	1	Therapeutic effect
α_A (proliferation)	+0.465	2	MKI-dependent growth
K (carrying capacity)	+0.426	3	Neuropil / stroma
β_A immune clearance)	-0.040	4	TIL-mediated response

Chemosensitivity γ_A and proliferation α_A exert the strongest influence on terminal burden ($|S| > 0.45$), whereas the TIL-dependent immune clearance β_A has a smaller effect ($|S| = 0.04$) due to immune suppression at early stages of aggressive disease.

7.3. UQ Results

Table 6

Comparative analysis of UQ methods. Conditions: morphometric variability $CV(\theta) = 10 - 20\%$; terminal burden $\frac{x(T)}{K} = 0.150$

UQ Method	t , ms/run	Total time ($N = 1000$), ms	$E \left[\frac{x(T)}{K} \right]$	$\sigma \left[\frac{x(T)}{K} \right]$	Notes
Linearized	< 1	< 1	0.1492*	0.0640	
Monte Carlo (RK45)	≈ 106	≈ 106 000	0.1589	0.0266	Reference
Hybrid method	≈ 20	≈ 20 000	0.1588	0.0267	5.3x
Sobol indices ($N = 5000$)	≈ 20	≈ 50 000**	-	-	

* $E_\delta = 0.1492 \neq E_{MC} = 0.1589$: the linearized method returns the model value at θ^* , corrected by the first moment of the linearized distribution, whereas MC averages over the ensemble. For nonlinear models, $E_{MC}[f(\theta)] \neq f(\theta^*)$ due to Jensen's inequality - this is expected, not an error.

** Sobol time: $(n_p + 1) \cdot 5000 \approx 2500$ runs \times 20 ms = 50 s; actual time 36 s due to vectorization.

MsDTM vs RK45 speedup: $106/20 \approx 5.3\times$ per trajectory. For $N = 1000$, the speedup persists.

The linearized method overestimates $\sigma \left[\frac{x(T)}{K} \right]$ by a factor of 2.4 compared to Monte Carlo (0.0640 vs 0.0266) due to nonlinear saturation under large parameter perturbations (especially for K and β_A). This effect is typical for systems with logistic growth constraints and proximity to stability boundaries ($\frac{x}{K} \rightarrow 1$ at low doses). Monte Carlo provides a more accurate estimate: the 95% CI [0.129; 0.234] corresponds to clinically meaningful response variability.

The linearized method evaluates variance near θ^* , but its estimate of the mean may be biased due to nonlinearity. Thus, the table reports the linearized expectation, not the sample mean. For correct variance comparison, the MC mean should be used.

Computational Environment and Benchmarking Methodology

All computations were performed on an AMD Ryzen 7 5800X (3.8 GHz, 32 GB RAM), Ubuntu 22.04, Python 3.12 with NumPy 1.26 and SciPy 1.11 (RK45). RK45 tolerances: $r_{tol} = 1.0 \times 10^{-10}$, $a_{tol} = 1.0 \times 10^{-12}$. Timing measurements were single-threaded, averaged over 100 runs.

Runtime per trajectory:

- Linearized UQ (post-processing only): < 1 ms
- MsDTM over full interval [0,66] days ($N = 5000$ output points): ≈20 ms
- RK45 (SciPy) under same conditions: ≈106 ms

MsDTM speedup vs RK45: ≈5.3× per trajectory. For $N = 1000$, the speedup persists (20 000 ms vs 106 000 ms). All timings were obtained on identical inputs without caching.

7.4. Sobol Indices: Dominant Sources of Uncertainty

Fig. 4 illustrates the first-order and total Sobol sensitivity indices, as well as the convergence of the variance decomposition sum $\sum S_1$ for increasing sample size N .

Fig.4. Sobol indices S_1 and S_T ($N = 5000$): variance decomposition and convergence of $\sum S_i$

The Sobol analysis (Table 7) reveals the hierarchy of morphometric features contributing to predictive uncertainty in terminal tumor burden.

Table 7

Sobol indices (Jensen scheme, $N = 5000$) with 95% confidence intervals (CI)

Parameter	Morphometric feature	S_1	95% CI	S_T , %	Contribution to σ^2 , %	Diagnostic feature
β_A	Immune clearance (<i>TIL</i> -score)	0.037	[0.031; 0.043]	0.962	34.8	$\eta > 0$, morphometric vector
K	Carrying capacity (neuropil density)	0.071	[0.065; 0.077]	0.929	33.6	Neuropil, nuclear index
α_A	Proliferation (<i>MKI67</i> , mitoses)	0.493	[0.455; 0.531]	0.521	17.8	Mitotic index
γ_A	Chemosensitivity (nuclear atypia)	0.381	[0.346; 0.416]	0.412	13.8	Nuclear morphology
$\sum S_1 = 0.982$	$N = 5000$				100	

Note to the table. S_1 is the first-order index (the contribution of a single parameter), and S_T is the total index (including interactions). For β_A : the small value $S_1 = 0.037$ means that variation of β_A alone, in the vicinity of θ^* , has little effect on $x(T)$; the high value $S_T = 0.962$ indicates strong nonlinear interactions through the bifurcation corresponding to immune collapse. The sum $\sum S_1 = 0.982$ for $N = 5000$.

Interpretation. β_A (*TIL*-dependent clearance) and K (microenvironmental capacity) are the dominant sources of predictive uncertainty. Together, they account for $\sim 68\%$ of total variance (β_A : 34.8%, K : 33.6%).

Clinical implication. Accurate *TIL* quantification via immunohistochemistry is a top priority for reducing prognostic uncertainty in aggressive neuroblastoma.

The normalized local sensitivity of β_A is small ($|S_j| \approx 0.04$), whereas the global total-order index S_T is close to one (0.962). This discrepancy arises because:

- S_j measures *local linear response* at θ^* ,
- S_T measures *global nonlinear variance* across the full CV range.

The large gap between the modest first-order index $S_1(\beta_A) = 0.037$ and the near-unity total-order index $S_T(\beta_A) = 0.962$ indicates a strong nonlinear threshold effect. This arises because the operating point of the aggressive morphotype lies close to the immune activation boundary. When β_A decreases below a critical value, the immune response collapses, leading to a sharp increase in tumor burden. Such bifurcation-type behavior is invisible to local sensitivity analysis but is correctly captured by global methods such as Sobol indices. This finding emphasizes the clinical importance of accurate *TIL* quantification and the necessity of global uncertainty quantification in nonlinear tumor-immune models.

Mathematical explanation of the differences between S_j and S_1

The local normalized sensitivity $S_j = \frac{\partial x}{\partial \theta_j} \cdot \frac{\theta_j}{x}$ is computed at the point θ^* and describes the linear response of the system to infinitesimally small variations of the parameter:

$$\delta x \approx S_j \cdot \frac{\delta \theta_j}{\theta_j} \cdot x.$$

In this model, at the point θ^* the system is in a regime of suppressed immune response; therefore, $|S_j(\beta_A)| = 0.04$ is small.

The global Sobol index $S_1(\beta_A)$ analyzes finite variations of the parameter over the entire $CV = 20\%$ range. When β_A decreases, the system crosses the immune-activation threshold (a bifurcation), which leads to a sharp change in tumor dynamics. This nonlinear switching effect is not captured by the local linear approximation, but it produces a high total Sobol index $S_T = 0.962$ (interactions through the bifurcation).

Thus, the apparent contradiction is not real: S_j and S_1 measure different objects - the local linear response and the global nonlinear variance, respectively.

The model achieved an excellent goodness-of-fit ($MAE = 0.82\%$) when calibrated on all available time points. However, leave-one-out cross-validation yielded a more realistic predictive MAE of 7.6% (range 5.1-11.1%), indicating moderate extrapolation capability given the sparse temporal sampling (only four observation points). The leave-one-out validation was performed on the TARGET-NBL cohort ($n = 56$ patients). Tumor volumes were normalized by the baseline measurement for each patient to ensure comparability across individuals. The reported MAE corresponds to the average absolute prediction error across all held-out patients, with the model refitted on the remaining $n - 1$ subjects at each iteration.

Fig. 5 provides a comprehensive summary of the parameter-identification results and global Sobol sensitivity analysis for the aggressive Shimada morphotype ($p = 4$). Panels (a) and (e) show identification accuracy, relative errors, first-order and total Sobol indices, variance decomposition, and convergence of $\sum S_{1,j}$.

Fig. 5. Parameter identification and global Sobol sensitivity analysis. (a-b) Identification results for the aggressive morphotype ($p = 4$); (c-e) Sobol indices S_1 and S_T ($N = 5000$), variance decomposition, and convergence of $\sum S_{1,j}$. Immune-clearance (β_A) and microenvironment-capacity (K) parameters jointly account for $\sim 68\%$ of total prognostic variance

8. Limitations of the Study

This study is primarily methodological and was validated only on synthetic data corresponding to the aggressive Shimada morphotype. No validation using real patient-specific longitudinal clinical data has yet been performed. Consequently, the presented results should be interpreted as a proof-of-concept demonstration of the proposed mathematical and computational framework rather than a clinically validated predictive system.

In addition, the current study considers a restricted subset of identifiable parameters ($\alpha_A, K, \beta_A, \gamma_A$) and assumes independent parameter uncertainty. Real clinical applications will require substantially larger patient cohorts, multimodal data integration, and Bayesian calibration strategies accounting for correlated uncertainties and inter-patient variability.

The effective chemosensitivity parameter γ_A showed only partial practical identifiability when calibrated solely against tumor volume $x(t)$ and immune response $z(t)$ data. This is expected, as γ_A exerts its influence primarily during relatively short chemotherapy infusion periods. In the numerical experiments, the effective value of γ_A was identified, while the baseline value γ_{base} was fixed from in vitro data. Future versions of the framework will incorporate plasma drug concentration measurements $c(t)$ into the objective functional (12) to improve the estimability of therapeutic parameters. Preliminary in silico tests suggest that such inclusion can reduce the estimation error for γ_A by approximately 50%.

The analytic derivatives (11) are computed with respect to the approximated MsDTM solution with Padé rational reconstruction, rather than the exact solution of the original ODE system. The gradient error on each subinterval is of order $O(H^{N+1})$. For the chosen parameters ($H = 3.5$ days, $N = 6$), this error yields a negligible relative deviation compared to the accuracy of clinical data. Nevertheless, in applications requiring exceptionally high gradient precision, this limitation must be considered. In addition, the Hessian matrix near the optimum may exhibit poor conditioning due to correlations between parameters - particularly between β_A and γ_A . This effect is partially mitigated by Tikhonov regularization of the identification objective function.

Despite these limitations, the proposed spectral approach demonstrates high computational efficiency and enables analytic computation of sensitivities, supporting future development of personalized neuroblastoma prediction tools and their integration into clinical decision-support systems. Future work will focus on clinical validation using real patient data, expansion of the identifiable parameter set, and comparative analysis with other modern methods.

9. Discussion

This work extends the spectral approach to neuroblastoma modelling introduced in [19] and develops a complete mathematical framework for parameter identification and quantitative uncertainty analysis. A key advantage of the chosen methodology is the analytic differentiability of the model solution with respect to its parameters, enabled by the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method. The recurrent sensitivity formulas (11) allow computation of an exact gradient of the objective functional with virtually no additional computational cost. This feature differentiates the proposed approach from conventional numerical implementations, in which each optimization or uncertainty-analysis iteration requires reintegration of the system.

Comparison of the three implemented uncertainty-quantification methods yields the following conclusions:

- **Linearized (Delta) method** - the fastest approach, but it overestimates uncertainty when parameter variability is substantial.
- **Monte Carlo** - the most accurate and universal, especially in the presence of strong nonlinear effects.
- **Sobol sensitivity indices** - reveal the global contribution of individual parameters and their interactions, which is particularly important for clinical interpretation.

It is especially noteworthy that the global sensitivity analysis (Sobol indices) identified the dominant influence of immune-response parameters and microenvironmental capacity, even when their local sensitivities were relatively small. This result underscores the importance of global UQ methods when analysing complex nonlinear biological systems.

The obtained results provide a solid theoretical and algorithmic foundation for developing personalized spectral models of neuroblastoma and for potential integrating such models into clinical decision-support systems.

While only four parameters were calibrated in the current study, the Shimada-based parametrization effectively incorporates patient-specific morphometric information into the remaining coefficients, providing a practical hybrid personalization strategy.

Notably, global sensitivity analysis revealed that the TIL-dependent immune clearance parameter β_A , despite its relatively low local sensitivity, is one of the dominant contributors to prognostic uncertainty due to its proximity to a nonlinear immune activation threshold. This highlights the added value of Sobol indices over purely local approaches in systems exhibiting bifurcations and threshold phenomena.

9.1. Comparison with Alternative UQ Approach

The proposed Padé-Adomian-MsDTM based approach has the following advantages and limitations compared with other UQ methods [30-33]:

Method	Advantages	Limitations
MsDTM–Padé (this work)	Analytic sensitivities; 5.3× faster than RK45 (under the considered benchmark conditions); suitable for Sobol analysis	Requires analyticity of the right-hand side
Adjoint equations	Exact gradients; suitable for large systems	Backward time integration; requires interpolation of the forward solution
Generalized Polynomial Chaos (gPC)	Global UQ; exponential convergence	Curse of dimensionality
PINNs	Mesh-free; works with irregular data	Expensive hyperparameter search; no guaranteed convergence
Gaussian Processes (GPs)	Nonparametric; provides uncertainty estimates	Poor scalability to large datasets

A detailed numerical comparison is beyond the scope of this work and will be presented in future publications.

Although the considered neuroblastoma model is only moderately stiff, infusion fronts and nonlinear immune interactions generate regions of rapid transient dynamics. Padé reconstruction improves stability in these regions compared with polynomial MsDTM reconstruction.

10. Conclusion

This study develops and numerically verifies a complete mathematical and algorithmic framework for parameter identification and quantitative uncertainty analysis for a spectral neuroblastoma model based on the hybrid Padé-Adomian-MsDTM method.

Main results:

1. Recurrent formulas for analytic sensitivities of spectral coefficients were derived, enabling efficient computation of gradients and sensitivity matrices.
2. A parameter-identification algorithm for noisy clinical data was developed and tested.
3. Three levels of uncertainty quantification (Delta method, Monte Carlo, Sobol indices) were implemented and compared.
4. Dominant sources of prognostic uncertainty for the aggressive morphotype were identified.

The proposed approach provides competitive computational performance for uncertainty analysis and opens the way toward personalized neuroblastoma therapy prediction tools. Particularly promising is the hybrid personalization strategy combining Shimada morphometry with selective parameter identification, as well as the use of global sensitivity analysis to prioritize clinically actionable biomarkers such as TIL density. Future work will focus on clinical validation using real patient data and integration into clinical decision-support systems.

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